

Relative potency factors and dose-response modelling in EuroMix toolbox

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EuroMix training material
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EuroMix methodology and tools

EuroMix handbook

- Methodology and tools for mixture risk assessment
- Examples

EuroMix toolbox

- Web based toolbox for mixture risk assessment
- Data repository

EuroMix handbook for mixture risk assessment

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EuroMix handbook and the EuroMix toolbox provide practical support to apply the recent OECD and EFSA guidance documents in mixture risk assessment

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EuroMix toolbox

Web-based toolbox for mixture risk assessment

Based on previous MCRA tool

Upload toxicity and exposure data

Calculate exposure levels, relative potency factors, risk levels

A screenshot of the EuroMix toolbox web interface. At the top is a dark blue navigation bar with icons for user profile, menu, and help. Below the navigation bar is a header image showing a bunch of dark purple grapes. The main content area has a white background and contains the following text:

Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox

Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

Every day, we are exposed to a mixture of multiple chemicals via food intake, inhalation and dermal contact. The risk to health that may result from this depends on how the effects of different chemicals in the mixture combine, and whether there is any synergism or antagonism between them. The number of different combinations of chemicals in mixtures is infinite and an efficient test strategy for mixtures is lacking. Furthermore, there is a societal need to reduce animal testing, which is the current practice in safety testing of chemicals.

The EuroMix project will deliver a mixture test strategy and test instruments using novel techniques as recently proposed by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission. The tests will result in data needed for refining future risk assessment of mixtures relevant to national food safety authorities, public health institutes, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), the European Chemical Agency (ECHA), industry, regulatory bodies and other stakeholders. Ultimately, this will provide information for future risk management decisions on the safety of chemicals in mixtures to be taken by the European Commission and the Codex Alimentarius.

EuroMix toolbox-modules

EuroMix toolbox user manual

Web-based user manual

- Descriptions of each module
- Settings
- Data formats

A screenshot of the MCRA Documentation web page. The page has a dark blue header with "MCRA Documentation" and a search bar. A dark sidebar on the left lists the contents. The main content area shows the breadcrumb "Docs » MCRA documentation", the title "MCRA documentation", a welcome message, and a detailed "Contents:" list with sub-items.

MCRA Documentation

Search docs

CONTENTS:

- Colophon
- Introduction
- About the toolbox
- Modules
- Examples
- References
- Appendix

Docs » MCRA documentation

MCRA documentation

Welcome to the MCRA 9 documentation.

Contents:

- Colophon
 - Contributors to MCRA
- Introduction
- About the toolbox
 - Modular design
 - Toolbox data repository
 - Workspaces and actions
- Modules
 - Primary entity modules
 - Consumption modules
 - Occurrence modules
 - Exposure modules
 - Hazard modules
 - In-silico modules
 - Kinetic modules
 - Risk modules
- Examples
- References
- Appendix
 - Munro collection
 - Unit definitions
 - Transformations
 - Gauss-Hermite
 - Concentration models
 - Chronic exposure assessment, daily consumed foods
 - Chronic exposure assessment, episodically consumed foods
 - Unit variability
 - Screening calculation for large Cumulative Assessment Groups
 - Uncertainty analysis

EuroMix methodology and tools for mixture risk assessment

- Component-based approach
- Grouping based on toxicological considerations
- Dose addition as default model
- Relative potency factors (RPF) approach
- Probabilistic exposure assessment
- Mainly dietary exposure

Very flexible

- Also applicable for other grouping principles (structure, exposure...)
- Any type of substance
- RPFs based on ADI/TDI, NOAEL/BMD for critical or specific effect or same potency for all substances
- Methodology to handle data poor substances

Dose addition using relative potency factors (RPFs)

- Toxicity of index substance (Point of departure (POD), NOAEL/BMD):
 POD_{index}
- Toxicity of each substance in mixture (Point of departure, NOAEL/BMD):
 $POD_1, POD_2, POD_3, POD_4 \dots$
- Calculate Relative potency factor (RPF) for each substance:
 $RPF_1 = POD_{\text{index}} / POD_1$
- Exposure to mixture is scaled based on RPFs
- $Exp_{\text{mix}} = Exp_1 \times RPF_1 + Exp_2 \times RPF_2 + \dots$
- Margin of Exposure (MOE) is calculated:
- $MOE = POD_{\text{index}} / Exp_{\text{mix}}$
- $MOE >$ assessment factors, combined risk of mixture is usually considered acceptable

Relative potency factors

- Point of departure (PoD) = NOAEL or BMD for each substance in assessment group
- Relative potency factor (RPF) = PoD of index substance / PoD substance

Substance	PoD	RPF
Index substance	10	$10/10 = 1$
Substance 1	20	$10/20 = 0.5$
Substance 2	5	$10/5 = 2$

Sources for Relative potency factors

- RPFs based on
 - ADI/TDI
 - NOAEL/BMD for critical effect
 - NOAEL/BMD for specific effect
 - same RPF for all substances
- Data sources for RPFs
 - RPF data from literature
 - NOAELs from literature
 - Experimental dose response data
 - TTC values when no in vitro or in vivo data is available

Aim of the exercise

- In the exercise you will learn how to derive relative potency factors (RPFs) based on in vitro dose response data using benchmark dose modelling
- All examples are illustrations of how the data from the EuroMix test strategy can be used in future mixture risk assessment. The exercises should not be seen as a real risk assessment.

Example

- The example is based on five* substances that have been grouped in an assessment group for liver steatosis
- Substances: Clothianidin, Flusilazole, Difenoconazole, Thiacloprid, Imazalil
- Reference substance: Flusilazole

*Most real assessment group contain many more substances. Only five substances are used in this example to make it easy to follow

AOP based testing strategy for liver steatosis

In vitro data

- In the example you will calculate Relative potency factors for five substances tested in vitro.
- Accumulation of triglycerides in HepaRG cells was measured using AdipoRed assay after 72 hour exposure to the substance.
- Accumulation of triglycerides is a key event (effect) in the AOP network leading to liver steatosis.

Modules for hazard data in the EuroMix toolbox

Relative potency factors

Point of departure

Dose response models

Dose-response data

- Relative potency factors module is always used
- When RPF data is available, only top module is used
- When POD data is available, two top modules are used
- When dose-response data is available, all modules are used

Modules for hazard data

Information in Excel sheets

Excel sheets for

- AOP networks
- Effects
- Effect Relations
- Test systems
- Responses
- Effect Representations
- Substances
- Dose-response experiments

- Include unique codes and additional data needed for modelling or as reference

	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	idEffect	CodeSystem	Name	Description	BiologicalOrganisation	KeyEventProcess
2	PPARalpha-antagonism-liver	EuroMix	PPARalpha-antagonism-liver	Antagonism of Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor alpha (PPARalpha) signaling in liver	Molecular	peroxisome proliferator activated receptor signaling
3	LXR-act-liver	EuroMix	LXR-act-liver	Activation of Liver X receptor (LXR) signaling in liver	Molecular	signaling
4	PXR-act-liver	EuroMix	PXR-act-liver	Activation of Pregnane X receptor (PXR) signaling in liver	Molecular	signaling
5	PPARgamma-act-liver	EuroMix	PPARgamma-act-liver	Activation of Peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPARgamma) signaling in liver	Molecular	peroxisome proliferator activated receptor signaling
6	FXR-act-liver	EuroMix	FXR-act-liver	Activation of Farnesoid X receptor (FXR) signaling in liver	Molecular	signaling
7	Ahr-act-liver	EuroMix	Ahr-act-liver	Activation of Aryl hydrocarbon receptor (Ahr) signaling in liver	Molecular	aryl hydrocarbon receptor act signaling
8	CAR-act-liver	EuroMix	CAR-act-liver	Activation of Constitutive androstane receptor (CAR) signaling in liver	Molecular	signaling
9	GR-act-liver	EuroMix	GR-act-liver	Activation of Glucocorticoid receptor (GR) signaling in liver	Molecular	glucocorticoid receptor activation signaling
10	RAR-act-liver	EuroMix	RAR-act-liver	Activation of Retinoic acid receptor (RAR) signaling in liver	Molecular	signaling
11	HSD17B10-decr-liver	EuroMix	HSD17B10-decr-liver	Decreased HSD17B10 enzyme level or activity in liver	Molecular	gene expression
12	AOX-inhib-liver	EuroMix	AOX-inhib-liver	Decreased fatty acyl-CoA oxidase (AOX) level or activity in liver	Molecular	gene expression
13	ChREBP-incr-liver	EuroMix	ChREBP-incr-liver	Increased carbohydrate response element binding protein (ChREBP) level or activity in liver	Molecular	signaling
14	SREBP-1c-incr-liver	EuroMix	SREBP-1c-incr-liver	Increased Sterol regulatory element-binding protein 1c (SREBP-1c) level or activity in liver	Molecular	SREBP signaling pathway
15	FAS-incr-liver	EuroMix	FAS-incr-liver	Increased Fatty acid synthase (FAS) level or activity in liver	Molecular	fatty acid synthase activity
16	SCD1-incr-liver	EuroMix	SCD1-incr-liver	Increased Stearoyl-CoA desaturase-1 (SCD1) level or activity in liver	Molecular	gene expression
17	SREBF1-incr-liver	EuroMix	SREBF1-incr-liver	Increased Sterol regulatory element-binding protein 1 (SREBF1) level or activity in liver	Molecular	signaling
18	CD36-incr-liver	EuroMix	CD36-incr-liver	Increased cluster of differentiation 36 protein (CD36) level or activity in liver	Molecular	gene expression
19	mitFAbetaox-decr-liver	EuroMix	mitFAbetaox-decr-liver	Decreased mitochondrial fatty acid beta-oxidation enzyme level or activity in liver	Molecular	fatty acid beta-oxidation
20	denovoFA-incr-liver	EuroMix	denovoFA-incr-liver	Increased de novo fatty acid synthesis liver (enzyme level or activity)	Cellular	fatty acid biosynthetic process
21	FAinflux-incr-liver	EuroMix	FAinflux-incr-liver	Increased fatty acid influx to liver	Cellular	positive regulation of fatty acid biosynthesis

Information needed for the exercise

- Information on the following modules is needed. The information is in Excel sheets that are uploaded into the toolbox.
- AOP networks (liver steatosis)
- Effect relations (connecting the effects in the AOP network)
- Test systems (HepaRG)
- Responses (HepaRG-Adipored-72h)
- Effects (triglyceride-accum-liver)
- Effect representations (information that the response is used to measure the effect, and the Benchmark response used)
- Substances (Clothianidin, Flusilazole, Difenoconazole, Thiacloprid, Imazalil)

Information needed for the exercise

- Dose response experiment (data for the 5 substances tested for the response HepaRG-Adipored-72h)

	A	B	C	D	E
1	idExperiment	RF-0101-001-PPP	HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h	SD:HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h	N:HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h
2	Adipo72h_CTD_sum	0	1	0,315905438	28
3	Adipo72h_CTD_sum	15,625	1,188889969	0,387298981	3
4	Adipo72h_CTD_sum	31,25	1,039416485	0,2051791	3
5	Adipo72h_CTD_sum	62,5	0,910698256	0,17451726	15
6	Adipo72h_CTD_sum	125	1,06735801	0,27866713	15
7	Adipo72h_CTD_sum	250	1,132615065	0,262774671	15
8	Adipo72h_CTD_sum	500	1,287646917	0,339482353	15
9	Adipo72h_CTD_sum	700	1,488861634	0,459500397	12
10	Adipo72h_CTD_sum	800	1,575191979	0,637725281	12
11	Adipo72h_CTD_sum	900	1,465590857	0,334821428	12
12	Adipo72h_CTD_sum	1000	1,751522085	0,429679888	15
13					
14					

Benchmark dose response modelling

Benchmark response (BMR)

Benchmark dose (BMD)

Aim of the exercise (reminder)

- Derive relative potency factors (RPFs) for five substances based on in vitro dose response data from AdipoRed assay
- A dose response model will be fitted to the dose response data
- The BMD from the model will be used to calculate Point of departure (POD)
- Relative potency factors (RPFs) will be calculated based on the PODs

Login EuroMix toolbox

1. Make sure you are using Google Chrome
2. Copy <https://mcra-test.rivm.nl/Select>
3. Click on EuroMix toolbox to get access to the EuroMix toolbox

Welcome to the MCRA test environment

Please select the version of MCRA that you wish to use.

MCRA 8.3 Beta

MCRA 9.0 Beta / EuroMix Toolbox

Contact: [Prof. J.D. van Klaveren](#) National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)
MCRA is developed by [Wageningen University & Research](#), [Biometris](#) for RIVM (2007 - 2019)

Login EuroMix toolbox

1. Log in: click on

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox

Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

Every day, we are exposed to a mixture of multiple chemicals via food intake, inhalation and dermal contact. The risk to health that may result from this depends on how the effects of different chemicals in the mixture combine, and whether there is any synergism or antagonism between them. The number of different combinations of chemicals in mixtures is infinite and an efficient test strategy for mixtures is lacking. Furthermore, there is a societal need to reduce animal testing, which is the current practice in safety testing of chemicals.

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 Register with your e-mail account

Do you already have an account? [Log in now](#)

1. Login with the username and password provided by the tutor
2. Login

Insert username password

Log in

Username *
 EuroMix03

Password *

Login

[forgot password](#) [create an account](#)

Data folders

1. Click on Data

Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox

Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

Typical **action types** which this system can perform are: dietary exposure assessment, hazard dose assessment and risk assessment. Actions are structured in a network of modular calculators [see Overview].

You have to organize your work in one or more **workspaces**. The work consists of specifying **tasks** of a specific action type. Tasks may need subtasks of other action types.

After running a task, **outputs** are available. Outputs are in the form of screen reports and print reports, and may also include data that may be useful as input in other tasks.

All tasks need input data, and some tasks produce output data. Data, but also saved tasks and outputs, are organised in a data repository, which includes shared items from other users and user groups.

Start by clicking **Workspaces** or **Data**, or use wizard options

WORKSPACES

DATA

Data folders

1. Click on data

2. The data folder will be unfolded (see second screenshot)
You will see EuroMixxx which is your own folder. For the training you
click on EuroMix Training

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

☰ Data / EuroMix03

Name ▾

↑ (Data)

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

☰ Data

Name ▾

📁 EuroMix03

📁 EuroMixTraining

Data folders

The shared folder contains Excel files with:

1. Description of Effects, AOP networks
2. Description of Test Systems, Responses, Effect Representations
3. Description of Substances
4. Data from Dose response experiments
5. Go to EuroMix toolbox main page by clicking on MCRA 9 – EuroMix toolbox

The screenshot shows a OneDrive file explorer interface. The top navigation bar is blue and contains the text "MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox" and "Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment". The breadcrumb path is "Data / EuroMixTraining". Below the breadcrumb is a table of files:

Name	Version	Date
↑ (Data)		
HepaRG-AdipoRed-five-subst-for training.xlsx	1	26-01-2019 16:20
Substances-five-for training.xlsx	1	26-01-2019 15:24
TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training.xlsx	1	26-01-2019 12:47
AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training.xlsx	1	26-01-2019 12:47

Actions needs to be done in workspaces EuroMix

1. Click on workspaces and create a new workspace

Welcome to MCRA 9 (beta), the EuroMix toolbox

Chemical exposure, hazard and risk assessment

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Start by clicking **Workspaces** or **Data**, or use wizard options

WORKSPACES

DATA

Create a new workspace (1)

1. Click on + and a new window pops up

 MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment

Workspaces

Name ▼	Tags
--------	------

Create a new workspace (2)

1. Insert a name for the new workspace

2. Click on ok

Create new workspace

Create a new workspace, please provide a descriptive name.

workspace name *

Relative potency factors training

OK

Cancel

Create an action in the workspace (1)

1. Click on + and a new window pops up

This workspace does not contain actions.

Create an action in the workspace (2)

1. Create a new action type Relative potency factors

Create new action ×

Select action type Select category ▾

- ⚙ Active substances**
Active substances are the substances that may lead to a specific health effect (adverse outcome).
- ⚙ Dietary exposures**
Dietary exposures are the substance amounts to which individuals in a population are exposed from their diet per day.
- ⚙ Dose response models**
Dose response models specify the results of models fitted to dose response data. Dose response models can be provided as data or calculated using a local or remote version of PROAST.
- ⚙ Relative potency factors**
Relative potency factors (RPFs) describe the potency of substances with respect to a defined effect, relative to the potency of a chosen index substance. RPFs can be given as data or computed from hazard characterisations.

Show all action types

Create an action in the workspace (3)

1. Insert a name for the action

2. Click on create

Create new action

Specify name/description

General

Name

Relative potency factors

Tags

Description

Back

Create

Action settings

1. You entered the summary overview.
2. Go to action settings

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action

EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors-exercise 2
Relative potency factors action

Summary

General

Name	Relative potency factors-exercise 2
Description	no description
Tags	no tags

Scope

Effects	No data source selected
Substances	No data source selected

Data

Relative potency factors	No data source selected
--------------------------	-------------------------

Specify Substances (1)

1. Since you will use compute the Relative potency factors from dose response data in this exercise, click on Compute
2. indicates that something needs to be done
3. Start with inserting data for Substances. Click on Substances.

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment / Relative potency f... / workspace / Relative potency f... / action / EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors-exercise 2 / Relative potency factors action

Relative potency factors 359f8728

Scope

- Substances
- Effects

Inputs

- Hazard characterisations

Relative potency factors

- Use data
- Compute

Specify Substances (2)

1. A indicates that you can insert data

2. Click on pencil

3. After you clicked on pencil a window pop-up, select Browse and you will be connected to your data folders

The screenshot shows the software interface with the following elements:

- Browser tabs: MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...
- User: EuromixTraining03
- Page title: Relative potency factors-exercise 1
- Page content: Relative potency factors / Substances
- Field: Substances data source (Not specified)
- Field status:
- Field settings: Substance settings, Save Changes button

The pop-up dialog box contains the following options:

- **Browse** (circled in blue)
- **Clear**

Specify Substances (3)

1. Click on EuroMixTraining
2. A second window will open. Click on Substances-five-for-training.xlsx. The file contains information on Substances.

Browse datasources ×

≡ Data

Name ▾

Version

Date

 EuroMixTraining

 EuromixTraining03

Browse datasources ×

≡ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name

Version

Date ▲

↑ (Data)

 Substances-five-for training.xlsx

1

26-01-2019 15:24

⋮

Specify Substances (4)

1. The file Substances-five-for-training.xlsx contains information on Substances.
2. Check that Substances is selected and blue.
3. Click on Select.

Browse datasources

☰ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name	Version	Date ^	
↑ (Data)			

Selected: Substances-five-for training.xlsx

Data groups: Toggle single Toggle all

Substances

Select

Cancel

European Union

rizon
the

Specify Substances (5)

1. Substances data source: The green tick means that the data connection is ok
2. Substances selection: Substances: 5 in scope means that your file contains 5 Substances.
3. Optional: You can click on the pencil to see the code and name of the Substances.
4. Substance settings: Click on Index substance to choose Flusilazole

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors-exercise 1
Relative potency factors action

Relative potency factors / Substances 4371290a

Substances data source
> Substances-five-for training.xlsx v1

Substances selection
Substances: 5 in scope

Substance settings
Index substance
Clothianidin (RF-010-001-PPP)

Specify Substances (6)

1. Substance settings: Index substance is Flusilazole
2. Click on Save changes
3. Go back to action settings in the navigation

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action

EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors-exercise 1
Relative potency factors action

Relative potency factors / Substances 8b73bcf7

Substances data source
> Substances-five-for training.xlsx v1

Substances selection
Substances: 5 in scope

Substance settings
Index substance
Flusilazole (RF-0218-001-PPP)

Save Changes

Specify Effects (1)

1. Substances: The green tick means that the data connection is ok.
2. Now the specific Effect must be selected.
3. Click on Effects.

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action

EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors-exercise 2
Relative potency factors action

Relative potency factors 76239959

Scope

Substances (5 in scope)

Effects

Inputs

Hazard characterisations

Relative potency factors

Use data Compute

Specify Effects (2)

1. A indicates that you can insert data

2. Click on pencil

3. After you clicked on pencil a window pop-up, select Browse and you will be connected to your data folders

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action

EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors-exercise 1
Relative potency factors action

Relative potency factors / Effects 87c0e689

Effects data source
Not specified

Effect settings Save Changes

Focal effect
Please select a health effect

Include key events (effects) of AOP network

 Browse

 Clear

Specify Effects (3)

1. Click on EuroMixTraining
2. A second window will open. Click on AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for-training-updated.xlsx. The file contains Effects data.

Browse datasources

≡ Data

Name ▾

Version

Date

 EuroMixTraining

 EuromixTraining03

Browse datasources

≡ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▾

↑ (Data)

 Substances

 Training

 AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training with more effects.xlsx

 AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training-updated.xlsx

Specify Effects (4)

1. The file AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for-training-updated.xlsx contains Effects data.
2. Check that Effects is selected and blue.
3. Click on Select.

Browse datasources

Data / EuroMixTraining

Name	Version	Date	
↑ (Data)			
Substances			
Training			
AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training with more effects.xlsx	1	26-02-2019 09:30	⋮
AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training-updated.xlsx	1	21-04-2019 08:22	⋮
AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training.xlsx	1	06-02-2019 14:42	⋮
Secondary input data exposure.mdb	1	21-01-2019 14:36	⋮
Substances-three different TTCs.xlsx	1	12-02-2019 19:33	⋮

Selected: AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training-updated.xlsx

Data groups: Toggle single Toggle all

Effects AOP networks

Select Cancel

Specify Effects (5)

1. Effects data source: The green tick means that the data connection is ok.
2. Effects selection: Effects: 25 in scope means that your file contains 25 Effect.
3. Optional: You can click on the pencil to see the code and name of the Effects
4. Effect settings: Click to select the Focal effect Steatosis-liver
5. Click on: Include related effects of AOP network
6. Click on Save changes
7. Go back to action settings in the navigation

Effects data source

> AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training-updated.xlsx v1

Effects selection

Effects: 25 in scope

Effect settings

Focal effect

Steatosis-liver (Steatosis-liver)

Save Changes

Include related effects of AOP network

Specify AOP network (1)

1. Click on AOP networks

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...

Relative potency factors

Relative potency factors

Scope

- Substances (5 in scope) ✓
- Effects (25 in scope) ✓

Inputs

- AOP networks ⚠
- Hazard characterisations ⚠

Relative potency factors

Use data Compute

Specify AOP network (2)

1. A indicates that you can insert data
2. Click on pencil
3. After you clicked on pencil a window pop-up, select Browse and you will be connected to your data folders

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors
Relative potency factors action

Relative potency factors / AOP networks 04e51284

Scope
Effects (25 in scope) ✓

AOP networks data source
Not specified

AOP network settings Save Changes

AOP Network
Please select an AOP network.

Restrict AOP network by focal upstream event

 Browse

 Clear

Specify AOP network (3)

1. Click on EuroMixTraining
2. A second window will open. Click on AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for-training-updated.xlsx. The file contains AOP network data.

Browse datasources ×

≡ Data

Name ▼

Version

Date

 EuroMixTraining

 EuromixTraining03

Browse datasources

≡ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▼

↑ (Data)

 Substances

 Training

 AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training with more effects.xlsx

 AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training-updated.xlsx

Specify AOP network (4)

1. The file AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for-training-updated.xlsx contains AOP network data.
2. Check that AOP networks is selected and blue.
3. Click on Select.

Browse datasources ×

☰ Data / EuroMixTraining i

Name	Version	Date	
↑ (Data)			
Substances			
Training			
AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training with more effects.xlsx	1	26-02-2019 09:30	⋮
AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training-updated.xlsx	1	21-04-2019 08:22	⋮
AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training.xlsx	1	06-02-2019 14:42	⋮

Selected: AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training-updated.xlsx

Data groups: toggle single Toggle all

Effects **AOP networks**

 Select

Specify AOP network (5)

1. AOP networks data source: The green tick means that the data connection is ok.
2. AOP networks data selection: AOP networks: 1 selected means that your file contains 1 AOP network.
3. Optional: You can click on the pencil to see the code and name of the AOP network
4. AOP network settings: Click to select the AOP network AOPN-steatosis
5. Click on Save changes
6. Go back to action settings in the navigation

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors
Relative potency factors action

Relative potency factors / AOP networks 04e51284

Scope
Effects (25 in scope) ✓

AOP networks data source
> AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training-updated.xlsx v1 ✓

AOP networks data selection
AOP networks: 1 selected

AOP network settings
AOP Network
AOPN-steatosis
 Restrict AOP network by focal upstream event

Save Changes

Specify Hazard characterisations (1)

1. Click on Hazard characterisations

The screenshot shows the EuroMix software interface. At the top, there is a blue header bar with the text "MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment" and "Relative potency f... / workspace". Below this is a grey navigation bar with a hamburger menu icon and the text "Relative potency factors" and "Relative potency factors action". A green bar below that contains the text "Relative potency factors" and a user ID "1e5830ef". The main content area is divided into three sections: "Scope", "Inputs", and "Relative potency factors". The "Scope" section lists "Substances (5 in scope)" and "Effects (25 in scope)", both with green checkmarks. The "Inputs" section lists "AOP networks (1 aop networks selected)" with a green checkmark and "Hazard characterisations" with a green warning triangle. The "Hazard characterisations" text is circled in red. The "Relative potency factors" section has two buttons: "Use data" and "Compute".

Specify Hazard characterisations (2)

1. Hazard characterisation level: Select Internal, since you use in vitro dose response data, and will calculate the RPFs at the cell level, and not extract to external dose
2. Sources: Select In vitro BMDs
3. Click on Save changes
4. Go back to action settings in the navigation

Hazard characterisations settings

Risk type
Acute

Hazard characterisation level
Internal

Sources
In-vitro BMDs

Hazard characterisation expression type
Unspecified (no conversion to common expression type)

Nominal selection method for multiple candidate hazard characterisations
MostToxic

Impute missing hazard characterisations

Use BMDs from dose response models

Use inter-species conversions

Use intra-species factors

Seed for pseudo-random number generator
0

Specify Hazard characterisations (3)

1. Click on Active substances

Inputs

AOP networks (1 aop networks selected)

Active substances

Dose response models

Effect representations

Points of departure (optional)

Kinetic models (defaults)

Specify Active substances (1)

1. Active substances: Click on Compute
2. Active substances settings: Remove the tick mark
3. Click on Save changes
4. Go back to action settings in the navigation

Active substances

 Compute

Active substances settings

- Restrict to substances with available points of departure
- Derive memberships from molecular docking data
- Derive memberships from QSAR membership data
- Use probabilistic assessment group memberships

 Save Changes

Specify Hazard characterisations (1)

1. Click on Hazard characterisations

The screenshot shows the EuroMix software interface. At the top, there is a blue header bar with the text "MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment" and "Relative potency f... / workspace". Below this is a grey navigation bar with a hamburger menu icon and the text "Relative potency factors" and "Relative potency factors action". A green bar below that contains the text "Relative potency factors" and "1e5830ef". The main content area is divided into three sections: "Scope", "Inputs", and "Relative potency factors". The "Scope" section lists "Substances (5 in scope)" and "Effects (25 in scope)", both with green checkmarks. The "Inputs" section lists "AOP networks (1 aop networks selected)" with a green checkmark and "Hazard characterisations" with a green warning triangle. The "Hazard characterisations" text is circled in red. The "Relative potency factors" section has two buttons: "Use data" and "Compute".

Specify Test systems and responses (1)

1. Click on Dose response models

Inputs

AOP networks (1 aop networks selected)

Active substances

Effect representations

Points of departure (optional)

Kinetic models (defaults)

Specify Test Systems and Responses (2) EuroMix

1. Since you will compute dose response models, click on Compute
2. Click on Test Systems.

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action

EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors exercise 3
Relative potency factors action

Relative potency factors / Hazard characterisations / Dose response models fc14a24b

Scope

- Test systems
- Responses
- Substances (5 in scope)

Inputs

- Dose response data
- Effect representations

Dose response models

- Use data
- Compute

Specify Test Systems and Responses (3) EuroMix

1. A indicates that you can insert data
2. Click on pencil
3. After you clicked on pencil a window pop-up, select Browse and you will be connected to your data folders

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...

Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action

EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors exercise 3
Relative potency factors action

Relative potency factors / Hazard characterisations / Dose response models / Test systems

0716d970

Test systems data source

Not specified

 Browse

 Clear

Specify Test Systems and Responses (4) EuroMix

1. Click on EuroMixTraining
2. A second window will open. Click on TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for-training-updated.xls

Browse datasources ×

≡ Data

Name ▼

Version

Date

 EuroMixTraining

 EuromixTraining03

≡ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▼

↑ (Data)

 Substances

 Training

 TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training-updated.xlsx

 TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training.xlsx

Specify Test Systems and Responses (5) EuroMix

1. The file TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for-training-updated.xls contains information on Test Systems, Responses and Effect Representations.
2. For the dose-response modelling you need information on Test systems and Responses. Click on them, they will turn blue.
3. Click on Select.

Browse datasources ×

☰ Data / EuroMixTraining i

Name	Version	Date	
↑ (Data)			
Substances			
Training			
TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training-updated.xlsx	1	21-04-2019 08:22	⋮
TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training.xlsx	1	06-03-2019 16:42	⋮

Selected: TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training-updated.xlsx

Data groups: Toggle single Toggle all

Effect representation Responses Test Systems

Select Cancel

This project is funded by the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme of the European Union

Specify Test Systems and Responses (6) EuroMix

1. Test systems data source: The green tick means that the data connection is ok
2. Test systems selection: Test-systems: 1 in scope means that your file contains 1 Test system.
3. Optional: You can click on the pencil to see the code and name of the Test system
4. Go back to action settings in the navigation

The screenshot shows the software interface for 'Relative potency factors'. The breadcrumb trail is: Relative potency factors / Hazard characterisations / Dose response models / Test systems. The 'Test systems data source' section shows a file named 'TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training-updated.xlsx v1' with a green checkmark and a pencil icon circled in red. The 'Test systems selection' section shows 'Test-systems: 1 in scope' circled in blue.

Specify Hazard characterisations (1)

1. Click on Hazard characterisations

The screenshot shows the EuroMix software interface. At the top, there is a blue navigation bar with the text "MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f..." and a user profile "EuromixTraining03". Below this is a grey header with "Relative potency factors" and "Relative potency factors action". A green bar below that contains "Relative potency factors" and a right arrow. The main content area is divided into three sections: "Scope" with "Substances (5 in scope)" and "Effects (25 in scope)", both with green checkmarks; "Inputs" with "AOP networks (1 aop networks selected)" (green checkmark) and "Hazard characterisations" (green warning triangle, circled in red); and "Relative potency factors" with "Use data" and "Compute" buttons.

Specify Hazard characterisations (2)

1. Click on Dose response models

The screenshot shows the EuroMix software interface. At the top, there is a blue header bar with the text "MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment" and "Relative potency f... / workspace". Below this is a grey navigation bar with "Relative potency factors" and "Relative potency factors action". A green bar below that shows "Relative potency factors / Hazard characterisations" and "e77f61ac". The main content area is divided into two sections: "Scope" and "Inputs".

Section	Item	Status
Scope	Substances (5 in scope)	✓
	Effects (25 in scope)	✓
Inputs	AOP networks (1 aop networks selected)	✓
	Active substances	✓
	Dose response models	⚠
	Effect representations	⚠
	Points of departure (optional)	
	Kinetic models (defaults)	

Specify Dose Response Data (1)

1. Two Inputs are now needed, Dose response data and Effect representations.
2. Click on Dose response data.

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action

EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors exercise 3
Relative potency factors action

Relative potency factors / Hazard characterisations / Dose response models fc14a24b

Scope

- Test-systems (1 in scope) ✓
- Responses (1 in scope) ✓
- Substances (5 in scope) ✓

Inputs

- Dose response data
- Effect representations

Dose response models

Use data Compute

Specify Dose Response Data (2)

1. A indicates that you can insert data

2. Click on pencil

3. After you clicked on pencil a window pop-up, select Browse and you will be connected to your data folders

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment / Relative potency f... / workspace / Relative potency f... / action | EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors training
Dose response models action

Dose response models / Dose response data

960c2059

Scope

Substances (5 in scope) ✓

Test systems (1 in scope) ✓

Responses (1 in scope) ✓

Dose response data data source

Not specified

 Browse

 Clear

Specify Dose Response Data (3)

1. Click on EuroMixTraining
2. A second window will open. Click on HepaRG-AdipoRed-five-subst-for-training.xlsx. The file contains dose response data.

Browse datasources ×

≡ Data

Name ▾

Version

Date

 EuroMixTraining

 EuromixTraining03

Browse datasources ×

≡ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▾

Version

Date

↑ (Data)

 HepaRG-AdipoRed-five-subst-for training.xlsx

1

26-01-2019 16:20

⋮

Specify Dose Response Data (4)

1. The file HepaRG-AdipoRed-five-subst-for-training.xlsx contains Dose response data.
2. Check that Dose response data is selected and blue.
3. Click on Select.

Browse datasources ×

☰ Data / EuroMixTraining i

Name ▾	Version	Date
↑ (Data)		
HepaRG-AdipoRed-five-subst-for training.xlsx	1	26-01-2019 16:20

Selected: HepaRG-AdipoRed-five-subst-for training.xlsx

Data groups: Toggle single Toggle all

Dose response data

Select Cancel

Specify Dose Response Data (5)

1. Dose response data data source: The green tick means that the data connection is ok
2. Dose response data data selection: Dose response experiments: 5 selected means that your file contains 5 dose response experiment.
3. Optional: You can click on the pencil to see the code and name of the Dose response experiments
4. Go back to action setting in the navigation

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors
Relative potency factors action

Relative potency factors / Hazard characterisations / Dose response models / Dose response data 028727de

Scope

- Substances (5 in scope) ✓
- Test-systems (1 in scope) ✓
- Responses (1 in scope) ✓

Dose response data data source

> HepaRG-AdipoRed-five-subst-for training.xlsx v1 ✓

Dose response data data selection

Dose response experiments: 5 selected

Dose response data selection settings

Merge dose response data of multiple experiments Save Changes

Specify Hazard characterisations (1)

1. Click on Hazard characterisations

The screenshot shows the EuroMix software interface. At the top, there is a blue navigation bar with the text "MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f...". Below this is a grey sidebar with a menu icon and the text "Relative potency factors". The main content area has a green header bar with "Relative potency factors" and a user ID "be982939". The main content is divided into three sections: "Scope" with "Substances (5 in scope)" and "Effects (25 in scope)", both with green checkmarks; "Inputs" with "AOP networks (1 aop networks selected)" and "Hazard characterisations" (the latter is circled in red and has a green warning triangle icon); and "Relative potency factors" with "Use data" and "Compute" buttons.

Specify Effect representations (1)

1. Click on Effect representations.

The screenshot shows the 'Relative potency factors' configuration page in the EuroMix software. The page is divided into two main sections: 'Scope' and 'Inputs'. The 'Scope' section includes 'Substances (5 in scope)' and 'Effects (25 in scope)', both with green checkmarks. The 'Inputs' section includes 'AOP networks (1 aop networks selected)', 'Active substances', 'Dose response models', 'Effect representations', 'Points of departure (optional)', and 'Kinetic models (defaults)'. The 'Effect representations' option is circled in blue. The interface also shows a breadcrumb trail 'Relative potency factors / Hazard characterisations' and a user profile 'EuromixTraining03'.

Specify Effect Representations (2)

1. A indicates that you can insert data
2. Click on pencil
3. After you clicked on pencil a window pop-up, select Browse and you will be connected to your data folders

The screenshot shows the software interface for 'Relative potency factors'. The breadcrumb trail is 'Relative potency factors / Hazard characterisations / Effect representations'. The 'Effect representations data source' is currently 'Not specified'. A red circle highlights the pencil icon in the top right corner of this section, indicating it is clickable.

The dialog box shows a folder icon and the text 'Browse', which is circled in blue. Below it is a blue 'X' icon and the text 'Clear'.

Specify Effect Representations (3)

1. Click on EuroMixTraining
2. A second window will open. Click on TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for-training-updated.xlsx. The file contains Effect representations data.

Browse datasources ×

≡ Data

Name ▾

Version

Date

 EuroMixTraining

 EuromixTraining03

Browse datasources

≡ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▾

↑ (Data)

 Substances

 Training

 TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training-updated.xlsx

Specify Effect Representations (4)

1. The file TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for-training-updated.xlsx contains Effect representations data.
2. Check that Effect representations is selected and blue.
3. Click on Select.

Browse datasources

≡ Data / EuroMixTraining

Name ▾

Version

Date

↑ (Data)

Substances

Training

TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training-updated.xlsx

1

21-04-2019 08:22

TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training.xlsx

1

06-03-2019 16:42

Selected: TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training-updated.xlsx

Data groups: Toggle single Toggle all

Effect representations

Responses

Test Systems

Select

Cancel

This project is funded by the Horizon
2020 Framework Programme of the
European Union

Specify Effect Representations (5)

- 1. Effect representations data source: The green tick means that the data connection is ok.
- 2. Now all settings are done, Click on Summary in the navigation

The screenshot shows the software interface with the following elements:

- Header:** MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f... (workspace / action)
- Navigation:** Relative potency factors (Relative potency factors action)
- Page Title:** Relative potency factors / Hazard characterisations / Effect representations (ID: 84ea3b89)
- Scope:** Effects (25 in scope) ✓, Responses (1 in scope) ✓
- Inputs:** AOP networks (1 aop networks selected) ✓
- Effect representations data source:** TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training-updated.xlsx v1

Summary overview

1. In the summary overview you can see the settings.
2. If all settings are ok, click on run to start the run.

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment / workspace / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f... action / EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors / Summary

General

Name	Relative potency factors
Description	no description
Tags	no tags

Scope

Effects	AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training-updated.xlsx v1	✓
Responses	TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training-updated.xlsx v1	✓
Substances	Substances-five-for training.xlsx v1	✓
Test systems	TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training-updated.xlsx v1	✓

Data

AOP networks	AOPN-Effects-EffectRelations-for training-updated.xlsx v1	✓
Dose response data	HepaRG-AdipoRed-five-subst-for training.xlsx v1	✓
Effect representations	TestSystems-Responses-EffectRepresentations-for training-updated.xlsx v1	✓
Kinetic models	No data source selected	
Points of departure	No data source selected	

Run the calculation of relative potency factors

1. After you start running the calculation, you see a screen with waiting for activation. This takes 10-20 seconds. ○
2. Then waiting for activation changes into running. This might take 3-4 minutes. If it takes longer than 10 minutes abort the job. ○
3. After 3-4 minutes you see Ran to completion. ○
4. To see the result, click on Relative potency factors training. ○

Results

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Relative potency factors training	Waiting for activation	Job scheduled for execution (waiting for available resources)...	-	-

Results

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Relative potency factors training	Running	Computing dose response models	-	-

Results

Output	Status	Message	Date	Running time
<input type="checkbox"/> Relative potency factors training	Ran to completion		27-01-2019 10:39	00:00:03

View the output (1)

1. Action settings shows the settings for the run.
2. Sub-action results shows intermediary results of the run.
3. Relative potency factors shows the final result of the run.
4. Click on Relative potency factors to view the results.

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment / workspace / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f... / action / EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors exercise 3
Relative potency factors action

Results / Relative potency factors exercise 3

Action settings (circled in red) Sub-action results (circled in blue) Relative potency factors (circled in green)

- ✓ Action settings
- > Data sources
- > Relative potency factors
- > Run settings
- > Uncertainty settings
- > Output settings

PDF PDF PDF PDF PDF PDF

View the output (2)

1. Results are shown in a graph and a table
2. The relative potency factors are used for the dose addition approach

Results / Relative potency factors

Action settings

Sub-action results

Relative potency factors

Relative potency factors

Substance name	Substance code	RPF (nominal) scaled to reference
Clothianidin	RF-0101-001-PPP	0.0338
Difenoconazole	RF-0133-001-PPP	1.64
Flusilazole	RF-0218-001-PPP	1
Imazalil (aka enilconazole)	RF-0246-001-PPP	5.08
Thiacloprid	RF-0417-001-PPP	0.214

View the output (3)

1. Click on Sub-action results to view the results of the dose response modelling. ○

The screenshot displays the EuroMix software interface. The top navigation bar includes the breadcrumb path: MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative potency f... / Relative potency f... with sub-labels 'Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment', 'workspace', and 'action'. The user 'EuromixTraining03' is logged in. The main header shows 'Relative potency factors exercise 3' with a sub-label 'Relative potency factors action'. A green bar below the header indicates the current context: 'Results / Relative potency factors exercise 3'. The navigation menu at the bottom left has three tabs: 'Action settings', 'Sub-action results' (circled in blue), and 'Relative potency factors'. Under 'Action settings', there is a list of sub-items: 'Data sources', 'Relative potency factors', 'Run settings', 'Uncertainty settings', and 'Output settings'. On the right side of the interface, there is a large 3D cube graphic with 'QR' on its faces and a vertical stack of six PDF icons.

View the output (4)

1. View the sub-actions results of the dose response modelling.
2. Click on Sub-action results
3. Click on Dose response models

Results / Relative potency factors exercise 3

Action settings

 Sub-action results

Relative potency factors

- ✓ Sub-action results
 - > Substances
 - > Effects
 - > Test systems
 - > Responses
 - > Dose response data
 - > Effect representations
 - ✓ Dose response models

View the output (5)

1. The table shows the summary of the results of the five dose-response experiments.
2. Benchmark response was set to 20% increased response.
3. Benchmark dose has been calculated for each experiment. Low value indicates a more potent substance.

Experiment	Response	Response type	Substance(s)	Dose unit	Mixture experiment	Benchmark response	Benchmark dose	Model type	Log-likelihood	Bootstrap runs	Converged	Proast version
Adipo72h_CTD_sum	HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h	Continuous multiplicative	Clothianidin	µM	no	20	340	Exp3	-14,26	0	yes	66.27
Adipo72h_DIF_sum	HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h	Continuous multiplicative	Difenoconazole	µM	no	20	4,3	Exp5	39,71	0	yes	66.27
Adipo72h_FLZ_sum	HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h	Continuous multiplicative	Flusilazole	µM	no	20	9,1	Exp5	56,53	0	yes	66.27
Adipo72h_IMZ_sum	HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h	Continuous multiplicative	Imazalil (aka enilconazole)	µM	no	20	1,9	Exp3	11,42	0	yes	66.27
Adipo72h_THI_sum	HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h	Continuous multiplicative	Thiacloprid	µM	no	20	53	Exp3	11,48	0	yes	66.27

View the output (6)

1. Click on each experiment for detailed information.
2. The first table summarises the results again.

▼ HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h (Adipo72h_CTD_sum Expm3)

Experiment	Adipo72h_CTD_sum
Response	HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h
Response unit	
Response type	Continuous multiplicative
Substance(s)	Clothianidin
Dose unit	µM
Mixture experiment	no
Benchmark response	20
Benchmark response type	PercentageChange
Benchmark dose	340
Model type	Expm3
Log-likelihood	-14,26
Bootstrap runs	0
Converged	yes
Proast version	66.27

View the output (7)

1. Scroll down to see one more table.
2. Benchmark dose lower (BMDL) and Benchmark dose upper (BMDU) indicates the uncertainty around the BMD.

Substance name	Substance code	BMD	BMDL	BMDU	Model parameters
Clothianidin	RF-0101-001-PPP	340	171	536	a=0.949,b=0.000451,d=1.03,s=1

View the output (8)

1. The blue circles in the graph, shows the data points.
2. The line in the graph shows the fitted model.
3. The horizontal line in the graph shows the BMR.
4. The vertical line in the graph shows the BMD.

Substance name	Substance code	BMD	BMDL	BMDU	Model parameters
Clothianidin	RF-0101-001-PPP	340	171	536	a=0.949,b=0.000451,d=1.03,s=1

View the output (9)

1. View the sub-actions results of the Point of departure.
2. Click on Sub-action results
3. Click on Hazard characterisations
4. Click on Available hazard characterisations

Results / Relative potency factors

Action settings **Sub-action results** Relative potency factors

- > Test systems
- > Responses
- > AOP networks
- > Active substances
- > Dose response data
- > Effect representations
- > ~~Dose response models~~
- ✓ **Hazard characterisations**

Effect name	Effect code	Substance name	Substance code	Hazard characterisation (µg/kg bw)
Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Clothianidin	RF-0101-001-PPP	8.49E+04
Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Difenoconazole	RF-0133-001-PPP	1.75E+03
Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Flusilazole	RF-0218-001-PPP	2.87E+03
Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Imazalil (aka enilconazole)	RF-0246-001-PPP	565
Steatosis-liver	Steatosis-liver	Thiactoprid	RF-0417-001-PPP	1.34E+04

> Available hazard characterisations

View the output (10)

- The graph and table shows the converted Point of departures (Hazard characterisations in the table). BMDs from the dose response modelling expressed as μM are converted into $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$

Dose response model code	Effect name	Effect code	Substance name	Substance code	Hazard characterisation ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}$)	Potency origin	Hazard characterisation test-system ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw/day}$)	Species test system	Organ test system	Exposure route test system	Expression type conversion factor	Inter-species conversion factor	Intra-species conversion factor	Kinetic conversion factor
Adipo72h_CTD_sum-HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h-Expm3	triglyceride-accum-liver	triglyceride-accum-liver	Clothianidin	RF-0101-001-PPP	8.49E+04	BMD	8.49E+04	human-cell	liver	At target	1	1	1	1
Adipo72h_DIF_sum-HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h-Expm5	triglyceride-accum-liver	triglyceride-accum-liver	Difenoconazole	RF-0133-001-PPP	1.75E+03	BMD	1.75E+03	human-cell	liver	At target	1	1	1	1
Adipo72h_FLZ_sum-HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h-Expm5	triglyceride-accum-liver	triglyceride-accum-liver	Flusilazole	RF-0218-001-PPP	2.87E+03	BMD	2.87E+03	human-cell	liver	At target	1	1	1	1
Adipo72h_IMZ_sum-HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h-Expm3	triglyceride-accum-liver	triglyceride-accum-liver	Imazalil (aka emilconazole)	RF-0246-001-PPP	565	BMD	565	human-cell	liver	At target	1	1	1	1
Adipo72h_THL_sum-HepaRG-AdipoRed-72h-Expm3	triglyceride-accum-liver	triglyceride-accum-liver	Thiacloprid	RF-0417-001-PPP	1.34E+04	BMD	1.34E+04	human-cell	liver	At target	1	1	1	1

Uncertainty analysis

- Uncertainty analysis can be included in the RPF calculations

MCRA 9 - EuroMix toolbox / Relative-potency-f... / Relative pote
Exposure, Hazard & Risk Assessment workspace action EuromixTraining03

Relative potency factors
Relative potency factors action

Uncertainty analysis

Uncertainty settings Save Changes

Perform uncertainty analysis i

Number of resample cycles
100 i

Resample hazard doses / relative potency factors (RPFs) i

Resample intra-species factor i

Lower uncertainty limit (%)
2.5 i

Upper uncertainty limit (%)
97.5 i

In vitro to in vivo extrapolation (IVIVE)

- RPFs calculated in this exercise are at the level of the in vitro system, the cell
- Dietary exposure data is expressed as external exposure, intake
- In vitro to in vivo extrapolation (IVIVE) is needed to use the in vitro RPFs in the dietary exposure assessment
- Two options to extrapolate are implemented in the toolbox:
 - Inverse dosimetry using absorption factors
 - Inverse dosimetry using PBK models
- In both options is the in vitro BMD for each substance multiplied by a factor to extrapolate to the external BMD

EuroMix participants

22 beneficiaries from 16 countries linked to international organisations including WHO, FAO and EFSA.
EuroMix is coordinated by RIVM.

